

M.TECH. IN IT AND COMPUTING AREAS WITH POSSIBILITIES IN INFORMATION ASSURANCE SPECIALIZATIONS: *THE INNOVATIVE FRONTIERS IN EDUCATION*

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Abstract

Information Technology is an important domain within Applied Science and Technology responsible for information affairs leading to collection, selection, organization, processing, management and dissemination. Information Technology has consist with different components and among these important are web technology, network technology, database technology, multimedia technology etc. As far as Information Assurance is concerned, this is fall under the area of network technology mainly within IT and partially database and web technology. The IT and Computing education in India offered in two platform, in one it is the area of Science (Applied) and in another it is fall under the area of Technology/ Engineering. This the IT programs comes with BSc/MSc and BTech and MTech nomenclature. However the BTech and MTech is also offered as BE/ME Degree in some respect. In recent past many universities in India have started the IT and Computing programs with specialization or Honors or Major. The importance of Information Assurance and Cyber Security is increasing; this paper is proposed about the Information Assurance major with MTech-IT and allied degrees keeping in mind Indian need in industry and policies of higher educational institutions. Paper highlighted the model curricula in this context as well. As a whole complete SWOT has been mapped of Information Assurance programs in MTech-IT and allied fields.

Keywords: Information Assurance, IT Security, Information Management, Systems Management, MTech Information Technology (Information Assurance), Indian Higher Education, HEIs, India

1.Introduction

Information Assurance is an advanced field of study and practice which is responsible for the designing, development, management, evaluation of information security. Information Assurance in short called as IA. Information Assurance term got popularity in last few years.

Previously the related known field was Information Security, Information Privacy, Information Technology (IT) Security, Cyber Security, Cryptography etc. The field and nomenclature Information Assurance is widely popular in united states and few western countries. Information Assurance is deals with both Computational Security and Manual Content security. Hence Information Assurance is focused with two major issues and concerns. The manpower and workers of Information Assurance related areas need to know both the areas [1], [5]. Cyber Security's technologies are the prime mover in Information Assurance whereas Information Privacy are also important and valuable in Information Assurance in managerial context. The field of Information Assurance is gaining popularity in different universities worldwide, but most of these universities offers the program as Science degree with BS and MS Degree. But in India few Science and Technology field is available both as Engineering and Applied Sciences Degrees (*and with the common degrees of BE/BTech as Engineering and BS/BSc as Science programs*) and among these important are Computer Science, Electronics, Information Technology etc. Hence as a Technical field Information Assurance may also offered as Engineering program in Indian context.

2.Objective and Agenda

This paper is about Information Assurance and completely theoretical in nature but strongly proposed as a policy paper. The following are few affairs in this regard—

- To learn about the basics of Information Assurance including its stakeholders and requirement.
- To learn about the basic features and function of Information Assurance so that we can why Information Assurance is needed as Masters level with reference to Engineering Degree.
- To find out few universities internationally those who are offered Information Assurance program at Masters level with MS/ MSc degree.
- To find out the way and suitable nomenclature of Information Assurance in Information Technology and Computing field.
- To learn about the Indian education sector with reference to Engineering Education to find out the feasibility in Information Assurance as an MTech Specialization.
- To learn about the existing Computing and IT Programs in India to help and design Information Assurance better way.

3.Information Assurance: Overview

Information Assurance is an emerging term in Information Science and Technology related to the privacy and security. Information Assurance is a broad field than that of Information security, Information Technology security and other areas of IT Security viz. Web Security, Database Security, Network security etc. The field Information Assurance is talks about the theory and practice of assuring, managing and assuring information and knowledge [2], [3]. The two sides of Information Assurance, viz. technological and manual solution becomes possible with the expert of Information Assurance. The uses, processing, storage, and transformation of information become easy with Information Assurance practice and principles. Information Assurance is widely available in developed countries as an alternative of cyber security. Hence, Information Assurance can be of following two methods based –

- **Computational/ Technological Information Security**
- **Manual Information Security/ Privacy.**

The following areas and tools are widely used in IT or Cyber Security and these are include but not limited to the following—

- **Database Security**
- **Network Security**
- **Web Security**

4.Information Assurance: Characteristics

Information Assurance become an advanced and super specialty areas of Information Science and Technology and thus many universities offers the programs leading to Bachelors, Masters, Doctoral Degrees and even Certificate, Diploma, Advanced and PG Diploma programs. Due to its need and requirement Information Assurance is gaining popularity worldwide and with the following features and characteristics of Information Assurance we can learn more; why the field becomes popular and available—

- Information assurance is dedicated to the information affairs towards information available to the respective individual in a right place [4], [7].
- Information Assurance is needed for protect data as well as privacy of unauthorized and illegal access.
- Technological security is also under the jurisdiction of this field of Information Assurance.
- Emerging cyber terrorism, cyber war etc concepts are also manageable with better and healthy Information Assurance practice.
- Information Assurance is essential for the mobile security as well as other allied security solutions specially the guidelines and principles etc.
- Design, development, and modernization of a secure and robust database and information systems are also become part of Information Assurance solutions.
- Cloud security including *infrastructure—trust* management become possible in solid and healthy Information Assurance practice in technological way.
- Strategic solutions in information and technological sectors become positively possible in Information Assurance solutions [8], [11].
- Information assurance deals with all the features and function of IT Security so it is dedicated to the malicious attack prevention including ethical hacking [6], [9].
- Fraud management system designing and Cyber forensic solutions are immediately possible with Information Assurance practice.
- Transparencies in information including public right on information are the solutions in Information Assurance.
- The holistic manual information system and computational information system security development are the core job in Information Assurance solutions.
- Management become core in Information Assurance and responsible for the designing, development as well as implementation of Information, cyber and IT related policies, framework and guidelines [10], [12].

Thus Information Assurance become urgency in almost all types of organizations and institutions regardless of private or government these day. As a result in India, Information Assurance should be offered in all the level of education to solve the market requirement in India.

5.Information Assurance and Allied Education

Internationally many universities have started academic and professional programs on Information Assurance and other allied field with the degree MSc/ MS/ BSc/ BS. Among the few universities few are listed in Table: 1.

Table: 1-Showing few international Universities offers Masters program in Information Assurance & Allied Field

Name of the Program
Davenport University
Nova South Eastern University
Sam Houston University
Florida Institute of Technology
George Mason University
Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University
FAIRLEIGH DICKINSON University
King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals
Hampton University
University of Central Missouri
Southern Utah University

6.India and IA Education in Computing and Information Field

Indian Higher Educational Institutes are growing rapidly, Pan India basis there are more than 40000 Higher Educational Institutes [11], [13]. Indian HEIs are categorized into Universities and College; and universities (refer Table: 2) are categorized into following—

- State Universities
- Central Universities
- Private Universities
- Deemed Universities etc

The Institute of National Importance is another kind funded, managed by the Indian Government towards excellence in a particular field (Refer Table: 3). The Computing as a program available in different universities and colleges and among few of them IT security and allied programs are offered.

Table: 2- Showing Indian Universities at a glance

Universities	In Numbers	Location
Central Universities	49	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Universities	399	Pan India with 28 States and UT
State Private Universities	334	Except some states and UT
Deemed Universities	124	Except some states and UT

Table: 3- The Institute of National Importance at a glance

INI/ Higher Educational Institutions	In Numbers	Location
Indian Institute of Technology [IITs]	23	Bhubaneswar, Chennai, Delhi, Gandhinagar, Guwahati, Hyderabad, Indore, Jodhpur, Kanpur, Kharagpur, Mandi, Mumbai, Patna, Ropar, Roorkee and Varanasi
Indian Institute of Information Technology [IITs]	23	Gwalior, Allahabad, Jabalpur, Kancheepuram, Sri City, Guwahati, Vadodara, Kota, Trichy, Una, Sonapat, Kalyani, Lucknow, Dharwad, Kurnool, Kottayam, Manipur, Nagpur, Pune, Ranchi, Surat, Bhopal, Bhagalpur
National Institute of Technology [NITs]	31	Agartala, Allahabad, Arunachal Pradesh, Bhopal, Calicut, Delhi, Durgapur, Goa, Puducherry, Hamirpur, Jaipur, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Jalandhar, Jamshedpur, Kurukshetra, Nagpur, Patna, Raipur, Rourkela, Sikkim, Silchar, Srinagar, Surat, Karnataka, Tiruchirappalli, Uttarakhand, Warangal
Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology [IESTs]	1 (4 are in process)	Shibpur (West Bengal)
Indian Institute of Management [IIMs]	20	Calcutta, Ahmedabad, Bangalore, Lucknow, Kozhikode, Indore, Shillong, Rohtak, Ranchi, Raipur, Tiruchirappalli, Udaipur, Kashipur
Indian Institute of Science Education and Research [IISERs]	05	Calcutta, Mohali, Thiruvanthapuram, Pune, Bhopal

Other Central Funded Higher Educational Cum Research Institutes	Approximately 150+	Pan India with 28 States and UT
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7.Engineering Education in India

Different kind of colleges viz. Engineering Colleges, Management Colleges, Architecture Colleges, Polytechnic Colleges etc are come under as Engineering program and under the jurisdiction of AICTE. It is important to note that there are enormous opportunity to offer the Educational as well as research programs on Information Assurance in India in several level and platform. As we aware that many international universities and institutes have been started Information programs due to ins need and importance therefore in India as well the Information Assurance and allied programs may be started positively.

Educational programs are changing internationally and come in a new shape. Different universities are moving towards introducing interdisciplinary and skill based programs. Universities from USA, UK and few other developed countries have started Information Assurance and allied programs as Bachelors, Masters and Doctoral Degrees. India as a biggest educational systems may introduce Information Assurance or allied programs in AICTE approved institutes (depicted in Table: 4). Importantly in almost all the discipline viz. Engineering, Management, Computer Applications etc Information Assurance and similar programs may easily accommodate.

Table:4 HEIs under the AICTE and possible programs in Health Informatics at a glance

Streams	Number of Institutes	Controlling Body	Total Intakes (as on 2015)	Remarks on Information Assurance potentiality
Architecture	177	COA/ AICTE	(Annual Intake of 11070)	May Not Possible
Engineering	6375	AICTE/UGC	(Annual Intake of 1903722)	Programs Information Assurance in CSE/IT may be started
Management	3217 (MBA)+ 600 (PGDM)	AICTE/UGC	(Annual Intake of 366439)	In Techno-Managerial programs, Information Assurance may be offered

Computer Applications	1469	AICTE/UGC	(Annual Intake of 110585)	Specialization of Information Assurance may be offered in MCA/BCA
Polytechnic	4276	AICTE	(Annual Intake of 1308008)	Special thrust may be given in higher semester for Information Assurance papers etc in CSE/IT related courses. Or full-fledged Information Assurance degree may be started

8.MTech Traditional in IT and Allied Fields with Reference to Information Assurance Specialization Potentialities—

Most of the university and colleges offered the departments and schools in following subjects and bellow mentioned areas as Engineering and Technology degrees including MTech Degrees—

- *Computer Science* (Computer Science is mathematical in nature and related with hardcore theoretical areas such as computing logic, software systems, hardware systems, tools, technologies responsible for Computing systems design and development)
- *Computer Application* (Computer Application is responsible for the design and development of software based applications)
- *Computer Science and Engineering* (It is a kind of merging domain and deals the domain of Computer Science and Computer Engineering. It is also related with hardware, mechanics, computing logics including systems development)
- *Information Technology* (It is kind of applied science responsible for information solutions viz. collection, selection, processing, management and dissemination with various technologies such as Multimedia Technology, Computing, Communication Technology, Networking Technology, and Web Technology)
- *Information Systems* (It is related with IT but focused on industry and managerial context)

And hence in all these subjects MTech/ME is offered and naturally due to the demand of the subject i.e. Information Assurance may be introduced.

Here two different approaches may be selected in first, the Information Assurance specialization may be started partially whereas in another approach it may be from 2nd year onwards. The specialization in Information Assurance may also nomenclature as following—

- Cyber Security & Information Assurance
- IT & Assurance

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- Information Systems and Assurance
 - Computer Forensic and Information Assurance etc

It is worthy to introduce various skill based components into the Information Assurance programs viz. Industrial Tour, tie-ups, Industrial Projects, and Skill based Internship for more value addition to the program.

9. Issues and Challenges

There are certain issues pertaining Information Assurance education at MTech in IT and Computing. The possible specializations may be as under

- MTech/ME-Information Technology (Information Assurance)
- MTech/ME-Computer Science and Engineering (Information Assurance)
- MTech/ME-Computer Application (Information Assurance)
- MTech/ME-Information Systems (Information Assurance)

In these programs, Information Assurance may be suitably added but for that apart from skilled manpower in Information Technology Security few other domains are also required viz. Law and Legal Studies, Management, Social and Information Studies etc, as the Information Assurance branch combines both technology and manual contents.

Information Assurance is broad and thus huge amount of financial support is required for the Division, Units and Departments running the program. From students end, the Information Assurance needs interdisciplinary knowledge as well. Initiatives from different stakeholders and related departments are also solicited. Unwillingness towards a new subject like Information Assurance is an important challenges for any interdisciplinary programs and Information Assurance as an interdisciplinary program and moreover skill based is an important challenge.

10. Conclusion with Suggestions

Information Assurance as an advanced program gaining popularity in different sectors, in India technological education is split into two; i.e. Science and Engineering. Hence Information Assurance may be started as a full-fledged degree viz. MTech/ MS- Information Assurance, if infrastructure and other equipments are available. Otherwise, the field can be started as a specialization in other IT and Computing subjects as prescribed above. Here both full-fledged degree and specialization can a treated as unique and innovative program; as worldwide M.Tech. is not offered and Information Assurance is available with MS/MSc Degree. And in India MTech is offered with other broader subjects as defined previously. In an existing university and departments MTech in Computing and IT related subjects, Information Assurance may be a good alternative. And even similar specializations may also be started with solid research or industrial atmosphere.

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